

REPRESENTATION OF SYNTACTIC UNITS IN THE PLACE OF MONOVALENT
NON-NUCLEAR DEPENDENT COMPONENT IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK
LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

This article focuses on the analysis of sentences with monovalent syntactic units in the position of the non-nuclear dependent (ÑD) component in the structure of English and Uzbek sentences; by means of componential and junctional models the researcher identifies the morphological features and syntactic relationships, the connection possibilities with other syntactic units of ÑD components. The article can take interest of researchers working on functional linguistics as well as those who learn the English language.

Key words: *syntactic connection, valency, subordinate connection, nuclear predicating, nuclear predicated, non-nuclear dependent, componential model, junctional model.*

INTRODUCTION

Structural analysis of a sentence device consists in characterizing the syntactic relationships of unidirectional units involved in a gap using junction models and visualizing differential syntactic characters, component composition, and morphological characteristics based on component models according to their position in a gap device.

In world linguistics, valence theory and comparative studies of languages have been a constant focus of linguistic scholars. In this regard, scientific-theoretical studies have been carried out by a number of scientists in general linguistics: European linguists L.Tener, J.Erben, G.Zandau, K.E.Zommerfeldt, A.Malchukov, B.Comrie¹; Russian linguists S.D.Katsnelson, N.N.Stepanova, V.Yu.Rozensveyg, S.M.Kibardina, E.V.Razova² it is worth highlighting the importance of the research carried out by.

Uzbek linguists also rely on verbocentrism to determine valence at the syntactic level. Including, N.Q.Turniyozov, I.K.Qo'chqortoev, R.Rasulov, M.M.Mirtojiev, S.H.Muxamedova, A.A.Abduazizov, D.T.Hojieva, M.K.Abuzalova³ valence has been researched within phonetic,

¹ Теньер Л. Основы структурного синтаксиса. Перевод с фран. – Москва: Наука, 2007. – 670 с.; Erben J. Abriss der Deutschen Grammatik. 9. Unverändert. Auf 1. –Berlin, 1966. – 316 s.; Зандау Г., Зоммерфельдт К.Е Семантические условия факультативности реализации валентности // Иностр. яз. в шк., 1972.– № 2– С. 21-27.; Malchukov A., Comrie B. (eds) Valency Patterns in the Language of the World. – Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter, 2011. – 265 p.

² Кацнельсон С.Д. К понятию типов валентности // Вопросы языкознания, 1987. – №3. – С. 20-32.; Степанова Н.Н. Особенности глагольной валентности южногессенского (Самарского) островного говора на Алтае в сравнении с современным литературным немецким языком. Автореф. дисс. канд. филол. наук.– Барнаул, 2002.-24с.; Розенцвейг В.Ю. Семантическая валентность слова, словообразование, синтаксис // Слово в грамматике и словаре. – Москва: Наука, 1984. – С.101-106.; Кибардина С.М. Валентность немецкого глагола. Автореф. дисс. канд. филол. наук.– Ленинград, 1988. – 34 с.; Разова Е.В. Семантика и валентность разрушения в современном немецком языке. Автореф. дисс. канд. филол. наук. – Вологда, 2003. – 25 с.

³ Турниёзов Н.Қ. Ўзбек тили структурал синтаксисига кириш. – Самарқанд: СамДУ, 1989. – 76 б.; Қўчқортоев И. Сўз маъноси ва унинг валентлиги (Ўзбек тилидаги нутқ феъллари асосида). – Тошкент: Фан, 1977. – 168 б.,

lexical, and syntactic line. Most of these works rely on only the lexical meaning of the verb at the lexical-syntactic level, focusing on the possibility of conjugation with other syntactic units within the sentence structure of the verb, and have been researched on this basis.

A syntactic line-scale analysis of the process of parsing a sentence into components and syntaxems. M. Mukhin, L.I. Jurevich, O'.U.Usmanov, Z.J.Mukhtorov, R.E.Kiyamov, Sh.S.Ashurov, D.T.Kubeysinova, V.B.Aristova, M.R. Jollibekova, M.S.Kayumova, M.M. Based on the scientific research of obloculovas, R.Asadov identifies syntactic valence in his study as follows: in this simple sentence the syntactic unit involved on the basis of one syntactic connection, no matter what form of the verb (in this case, the word category does not matter) - the one-valence component, the syntactic unit involved on the basis of two syntactic connections – the two-valence component, the syntactic unit⁴.

When determining the valence of components at the syntactic level, the number of syntactic connections of the syntactic units involved in the structure of the sentence is taken into account. Based on this idea, syntactic units are considered monovalent or monovalent components if they participate in the structure of a sentence based on one syntactic relationship. Based on the analysis of examples collected from the literature, it can be observed that univalent components appear in the syntactic positions of core components (NP1.NP2), non-core subordinate (ÑD) and non-core predicative 2 components in the sentence device.

Methods and materials

In this article, we will try to analyze sentences with monovalent syntactic units in the place of a non-nuclear dependent component based on junctional and component models. We also use various transformation methods.

In traditional grammar, the syntactic analysis of the sentence is divided into primary and secondary clauses. In this method, while analyzing the sentence into parts, syntactic relations are not mentioned and syntactically separated units are not distinguished. The phenomenon of elementary syntactic units is not taken into account in the concept of sentence fragments. In the analysis of the structure of the sentence by dividing it into components, it is important to determine the mutual syntactic relations of the syntactic units in the sentence, and it is also of great importance to distinguish the identified syntactic relations from each other. The syntactic relations determined between the components or syntactic units create ample conditions for determining the differential syntactic features of the components involved in the sentence. Such differential syntactic signs are determined using the method of contrasting or contrasting components in the syntagmatic direction.

In this research work, the description of the mutual syntactic relations of the components in the sentence is carried out with the help of junctional models. The term junction model is derived

Расулов Р. Ўзбек тилидаги ҳолат феъллари ва уларнинг облигатор валентликлари. – Тошкент, 1989. – 82 б.; Миртожиев М. Ўзбек тилидаги феъл валентликлари. – Тошкент, 2007. – Б.48.; Мухамедова С. Ўзбек тилида ҳаракат феълларининг семантик ва валентлик хусусиятлари. Филол. фан. док-ри. дис.автореф. – Тошкент, 2007. – 40 б.; Абдуазизов А.А. О фонологической валентности // Филологиянинг долзарб муаммолари. – Тошкент, 2008. – С.14-21.; Ходжиева Д.Т. Изменение структурно-функциональной характеристики и валентности глагольных словосочетаний в истории английского языка. Автореф. дисс. канд. филол. наук.– Самарканд, 2011. – 27 с.; Абузалова М. Грамматическая валентность некатегориальных форм // Filologiya masalalari. Azerbaijan milliy Ilmlar Akademiyasi, 2011. – В. 414-418.

⁴ Асадов Р.М. Инглиз тили содда гап қурилмаларида моновалентли ва поливалентли компонентларнинг синтаксем таҳлили. Фил.фан.бўйича фалсафа доктори (PhD) дисс. автореф. – Тошкент. 2018. – Б. 12.

from the Latin word "junction" and in Uzbek means connection, connection⁵. This model is built in a horizontal direction and represents the real distribution of the components of the sentence and their interdependence. In the article, we visually express syntactic relations of the syntactic units involved in the structure of the sentence with the help of junctional models, that is, in them, core predicative, subordinating, coordinating, zero predicative, introductory, non-nuclear predicative, appositive relations are defined. In the study of non-nuclear dependent components, we focus on subordinate communication.

The parts that are the basis of the sentence, i.e. the core, are called core components⁶, in traditional grammars, this is referred to as the head of the sentence. Since there are two core components, core predicative 1 (subject - subject) and core predicative 2 (section - Predicate) based on the order of their placement in the sentence⁷ terms are used.

Non-nuclear subordinate components are secondary parts of the sentence - parts with the function of determiner, complement, and case. The reason why we call them non-nuclear subordinates is that they cannot form the basis of a sentence, and any governor is subordinate to a clause and is connected to it on the basis of a subordinate relationship. Non-nuclear dependent components can be connected not only to core components, but also to a second dependent component, in which case a certain element can be both a base and a subordinate part in one sentence.

The special feature of subordinate components is that they turn simple compound sentences into extended sentences, clarify and complete the content of the sentence. W.N.Francis subordinating or modifying compounds⁸, states that. Sh. Ashurov says that the subordinating relation serves to differentiate between the dominant and subordinate components in the structure of word combinations⁹ admits.

According to some linguists, the presence of a subordinate clause in a sentence is expressed by a transitive verb¹⁰. However, an intransitive verb can also have a subordinate component¹¹, for example *to go* is an intransitive verb, "*I go to the bank on Mondays*" in the sentence *to the bank* and *on Mondays* syntactic units *go* is subject to the verb. Also, participles and other clauses expressed by word groups other than verbs can have a subordinate component. The subordinate component is observed in the cases of preposition (previous) and postposition (following) in relation to the main component.

Results and discussions

In this article, we will demonstrate the role and representation of subordinate components based on examples.

1. The man in the painting looked inquiringly at the Prime Minister (JRHP, 2).

⁵ Мухин А.М. Модели внутренних синтаксических связей предложений // Вопросы языкознания. – Москва: 1970.– №4.– С.68-69.

⁶ Мухин А.М. Структура предложений и их модели. – Ленинград: Наука, 1968. – С. 98.

⁷ Мухин А. М. Функциональный синтаксис. – СПб.: Наука, 1999. – С. 106.; Усмонов Ў.У. Гап таҳлилига янгича ёндашув // Ҳалқаро илмий-назарий анжуман. – Самарқанд: СамДЧТИ, 2004. – Б. 105-108.

⁸ Frensis W.N. The Structure of American English. – Textbook Publishers, 2003. – 614 p. https://books.google.co.uz/books/about/The_Structure_of_American_English.html?id

⁹ Ашуров Ш.С. Инглиз ва ўзбек тилларида кесим типологияси// Филол. фан. номзод. диссертация.– Самарқанд, 2007. – С. 39.

¹⁰ Почепцов Г.Г. Конструктивный анализ в структуре предложения. – Киев: Вища школа, 1971. – С. 59-60.

¹¹ Slobodkina N.A., Abduraimova B.Yu., Rustamova Z.N., Tukliyeva G.N. Practical English Grammar. – Tashkent: O'zbekiston Milliy Ensiklopediyasi, 2007. – P. 196.

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2. *Olive shouted encouragement (RRHC, 20).*
3. **Harry Potter was snoring loudly (JRHP, 25).**
4. **He had been sitting in a chair beside (JRHP, 25).**
5. *I remembered old footage of the ill-fated Hindenburg ... (RRHC, 67).*

Omitting subordinate components usually does not significantly affect the meaning of the sentence. Below, we define by dropping subordinate clauses using the transformation method:

- 1) **The man in the painting looked inquiringly at the Prime Minister → The man ... looked ...;**
- 2) *Olive shouted encouragement → Olive shouted ...;*
- 3) **Harry Potter was snoring loudly → Harry Potter was snoring ...;**
- 4) **He had been sitting in a chair beside → He had been sitting ...;**
- 5) *I remembered old footage of the ill-fated Hindenburg ... → I remembered ... footage of ... Hindenburg → I remembered*

In the given sentences, the non-nuclear dependent (ÑD) components are connected to the core predicative 2 (NP2) component on the basis of a subordinate relationship. In this case, intransitive verbs – *looked (1), was snoring (3), had been sitting (4)* expressed in syntactic units *inquiringly (1), loudly (3)*, represented by a prepositional noun **at the Prime Minister (1), in a chair (4) elements have been subjected. Expressed by a transitive verb NP₂ – shouted (2), remembered (5)** components are represented by nouns ÑD components – *encouragement (2), footage (5)* entered into a syntactic relationship in the base of subordinate communication. In all these sentences, ÑD elements subordinate to NP2 components are in postpositional position. Also represented by the noun NP₁ – **The man (1)** and ÑD – **in a chair (4), footage (5)** the syntactic units subordinated to its components are in the construction of preposition + noun – *in the painting (1), of Hindenburg (5)* or adverb *beside (4)* is located after the base component. When the syntactic unit ÑD occurs with an adjective, it is placed before the governing clause: *old* adjective *footage* element, *ill-fated* compound adjective *Hindenburg* it can be shown in the junction and component model of sentences that it is connected to the lexeme on the basis of a subordinate relationship.

(1) The man in the painting looked inquiringly at the Prime Minister.			
	J .M.	$\frac{NP_1}{S} \cdot \frac{\tilde{N}D}{prS} \cdot \frac{NP_2}{Vf} \cdot \frac{\tilde{N}D}{Adv} \cdot \frac{\tilde{N}D}{prS}$	C.M.
(2) <i>Olive shouted encouragement</i>			
	J .M.	$\frac{NP_1}{S} \cdot \frac{NP_2}{Vf} \cdot \frac{\tilde{N}D}{S}$	C.M.
(3) Harry Potter was snoring loudly.			
	J .M.	$\frac{NP_1}{S} \cdot \frac{NP_2}{auxV_{con}} \cdot \frac{\tilde{N}D}{Adv}$	C.M.
(4) He had been sitting in a chair beside			

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	J .M.	$\underline{NP_1} \cdot \underline{NP_2} \cdot \underline{\tilde{N}D} \cdot \underline{\tilde{N}D}$ Pn _p auxVp ₁ prS Adv	C.M.
(5) <i>I remembered old footage of the ill-fated Hindenburg</i>			
	J .M.	$\underline{NP_1} \cdot \underline{NP_2} \cdot \underline{\tilde{N}D} \cdot \underline{\tilde{N}D} \cdot \underline{\tilde{N}D} \cdot \underline{\tilde{N}D}$ Pn _p Vf A S A prS	C.M.

In the following sentences, the subordinate components are connected to the non-nuclear predicative 2 ($\tilde{N}D$) component in the sentence and its subordinate components using a subordinate relation:

6. *We rowed taking turns at the oars to stave off exhaustion (RRHC, 18).*

7. *... he had climbed out brushing ash from the sleeves of his long pin-striped cloak (JRHP, 2).*

The cited sixth sentence has three subordinate components, and the seventh sentence has five subordinate components, which we separate by the omission transformation:

6) *We rowed taking turns at the oars to stave off exhaustion* → *We rowed taking turns at the oars ...* → *We rowed taking turns ... to stave off exhaustion;*

7) *... he had climbed out brushing ash from the sleeves of his long pin-striped cloak* → *he had climbed out brushing ash* → *he had climbed out brushing ash from the sleeves ...* → *he had climbed out brushing ash from the sleeves of ... cloak* → *he had climbed out brushing ash from the sleeves of his ... cloak.*

In the sixth sentence $\tilde{N}D$ – at the oars and to stave off if the non-nuclear predicate is subject to 2 components, exhaustion element is another $\tilde{N}D$ – to stave off enters into a subordinate relationship with the element. In this sentence to stave off It is subordinate to the component before it, and it is the main component to the next component.

In the seventh sentence $\tilde{N}P_2$ because it is expressed by a transitive verb, it is the first subordinate to it $\tilde{N}D$ – ash noun without a preposition, in the second $\tilde{N}D$ – from the sleeves formed with a prepositional noun. Also in this sentence $\tilde{N}D$ – sleeves component of cloak the governing body in relation to the component, $\tilde{N}D$ – of cloak however, his, long and pin-striped and is their main component. So, in this sentence, two syntactic units perform the function of both the ruler and the subordinate clause at the same time. This situation is reflected in junction and component models as follows:

(6) <i>We rowed taking turns at the oars to stave off exhaustion</i>			
	J.M.		
$\underline{NP_1} \cdot \underline{NP_2} \cdot \underline{\tilde{N}P_2} \cdot \underline{\tilde{N}D} \cdot \underline{\tilde{N}D} \cdot \underline{\tilde{N}D}$ Pn _p Vf Vp ₁ S prS V _{inf} S	C.M.		
(7) <i>... he had climbed out brushing ash from the sleeves of his long pin-striped cloak</i>			
	J.M.		

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$\underline{NP}_1 . \underline{NP}_2 . \check{NP}_2 . \check{ND} . \check{ND} . \check{ND} . \check{ND} . \check{ND}$	C.M.
Pn _p auxVp ₂ Vp ₁ S prS Pn _{ps} A A prS	

In the structure of an English sentence, non-nuclear dependent components are identified by the syntactic units represented by the noun phrase. They are mainly represented by adjectives and are placed before the main component, as well as with pronouns and numbers that can be placed both before and after the main component.

- 8. ... bright green flames burst into life (JRHP, 2).
- 9. I ... said a silent goodbye (RRHC, 21).
- 10. ... we had more than fifty eyewitnesses (JRHP, 7)
- 11. The minute hand on the alarm clock reached the number twelve ... (JRHP, 29).
- 12. twenty minutes later I asked for it back again (RRHC, 20).
- 13. He had never tasted anything like it before (JRHP, 31).

As a subordinate clause, the adjective is simple – *silent* (9) or compound – **bright green** (8) no matter what, the governor is from the block – *flames* (8), *goodbye* (9) placed first. Numbers means to count, to count – *fifty* (10), *twenty* (12) from the governor (**eyewitnesses**, *minutes*) before, order means number – *twelve* (11) hokim from the piece (*number*) comes later. In the twelfth sentence, number is involved – *twenty minutes later* the combination is a whole syntactic unit, because these three lexical units together when there will be an answer to the question. In the next sentence *anything* subordinate component *had tasted* connected with a transitive verb on the basis of a subordinate relationship and at the same time *like it* is the main component compared to the component.

The junctional and component models of the following sentences show the relations and morphological properties of syntactic units:

(8) ... bright green flames burst into life		
	J .M.	$\check{ND} . \underline{NP}_1 . \underline{NP}_2$ C.M. A S VfprS
<i>(9) I ... said a silent goodbye</i>		
	J .M.	$\underline{NP}_1 . \underline{NP}_2 . \check{ND} . \check{ND}$ C.M. Pn _p Vf A S
(10) ... we had more than fifty eyewitnesses.		
	J .M.	$\underline{NP}_1 . \underline{NP}_2 . \check{ND} . \check{ND} . \check{ND}$ C.M. Pn _p Vf Adv cjNm S
(11) The minute hand on the alarm clock reached the number twelve		
	J .M.	$\underline{NP}_1 . \check{ND} . \underline{NP}_2 . \check{ND} . \check{ND}$ C.M. S prS Vf S Nm
<i>(12) twenty minutes later I asked for it back again</i>		

	J .M.	$\frac{\tilde{N}D}{NmSAdv} \cdot \frac{NP_1}{Pnp} \cdot \frac{NP_2}{Vf} \cdot \frac{\tilde{N}D}{prPnp} \cdot \frac{\tilde{N}D}{Adv}$ C.M.
(13) He had never tasted anything like it ...		
	J .M.	$\frac{NP_1}{Pnp} \cdot \frac{\tilde{N}D}{Adv_{ng}} \cdot \frac{NP_2}{auxVp_2} \cdot \frac{\tilde{N}D}{Pn_{ind}} \cdot \frac{\tilde{N}D}{cjPnp}$ C.M.

In our next examples, we will consider the case of inversion when the non-nuclear dependent component is expressed by an infinitive conjunction:

14. The Prime Minister did not know what to say (JRHP, 7).

15. Downstairs in the living room his Uncle Vernon shouted (JRHP, 29).

In the given sentence, $\tilde{N}D$ is an infinitive conjunction – *what to say* (14) is represented by and is in one syntactic place, because it is an answer to one question and NP_2 – **did not know is connected to the component using a subordinate relation. In the next sentence $\tilde{N}D$ – downstairs logical accented, inverted and located at the beginning of the sentence, NP_2 – **shouted subject to the component. In English, only a dependent clause subject to NP_2 can appear at the beginning of a sentence, NP_1 or $\tilde{N}D$ is not a subordinate clause. This is it sentence in the living room we cannot call a syntactic unit a monovalent subordinate component because it downstairs is explaining the element. Commentators explicitly and implicitly enter into three syntactic relations and are trivalent components ¹². In this sentence **Uncle Vernon there is also an appositive connection between.** Since we are studying monovalent syntactic units in our article, we will not dwell on this issue in detail.****

We express the junction and component models of sentences as follows:

(14) The Prime Minister did not know what to say		
	J .M.	$\frac{NP_1}{S} \cdot \frac{NP_2}{ngVf} \cdot \frac{\tilde{N}D}{Pn_{rl}V_{inf}}$ C.M.
(15) Downstairs in the living room his Uncle Vernon shouted.		
	J .M.	$\frac{\tilde{N}AD}{Adv} \cdot \frac{\tilde{N}D}{prS} \cdot \frac{\tilde{N}D}{Pnp} \cdot \frac{\tilde{N}AP_1}{S} \cdot \frac{NP_1}{S} \cdot \frac{NP_2}{Vf}$ C.M.

From the analysis of the examples collected from the works of art, it is known that in English, non-nuclear subordinate components can appear in all places of the sentence, they can depend on both the core component and the subordinate component, and they are in preposition or postposition in relation to the main component. Also, a univalent subordinate clause can be represented by a noun, adjective, number, infinitive conjunction and pronoun.

The expression of non-nuclear dependent components in the Uzbek language is partially different from the English language. In the Uzbek language, the subordinate components are

¹² Асадов Р.М. Синтаксическая валентность на примере синтаксического анализа трёхвалентных элементов в позиции неядерного аппозитивного предизирующего компонента (NAP_1) // Вестник ЧелГУ. 2016, №9 (391). – С. 25-35.

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mainly placed before the dominant components, that is, they come in the preposition position, the postposition position is almost never observed.

In the following examples, we will analyze the subordinate components connected to the transitive verb:

1. ... Bayna momo jelagi bilan yuzini ayollardan to'sib oldi (ENShTB, 6).
2. Gullarni uch kun oldin qizi bolalar bog'chasidan ... uzib kelgandi (ENYH, 14).
3. Bolalar nega hech narsa yeyishmaydi (QA, 7).
4. ... maysalarning jozibasini o'ziga singdirolmadi (ENYH, 10).
5. Buning yorqin misolini Hasan ikki marta boshidan o'tkazdi (QA, 90).

NP2 is used in the given sentences – to'sib oldi (1), uzib kelgandi (2), yeyishmaydi (3), o'ziga singdirolmadi (4), boshidan o'tkazdi (5) first of all, since syntactic units are formed from transitive verbs, Kimni or Nimani The answer to the question requires an indirect complement. As mentioned in the first chapter, most linguists divide such verbs into two-, three-, and four-valence groups, based on the number of actants, based on the lexical meaning of the verb. However, we define syntactic valence based on the number of syntactic links. Accordingly, each syntactic unit in these sentences is univalent, because they enter into a syntactic relationship one at a time.

Three ÑD components in the first sentence (jelagi bilan, yuzini, ayollardan) are available, all subject to NP2, and their agreement suffixes (-ni, -dan) and auxiliary (bilan) connected using In the second sentence, three subordinate components are involved, one of which is an actant (Gullarni) accusative (-ni), two are circaconstant uch kun oldin – adverb phrase and bolalar bog'chasidan – formed by using the noun in the exit clause and uzib kelgandi entered into a subordinate relationship with the fragment.

In the third and fourth examples, the subordinate component is the verb in the form without division (yeyishmaydi) subordinated. Infinitive pronoun (hech narsa) represented by the actant. Circonstant is an interrogative pronoun (nega) represented. In the next sentence, the noun in the accusative case (jozibasini) The subordinate clause activated by (maysalarning) has also performed the role of the governor in relation to the subordinate component. The fifth sentence contains four ÑD, two of them (misolini, ikki marta) NP2 two of them (Buning, yorqin) ÑD component (misolini) has been subordinated.

The junction and component models of sentences are as follows:

(1) ... Bayna momo jelagi bilan yuzini ayollardan to'sib oldi		
	J .M.	$\underline{NP_1} \cdot \underline{\check{N}D} \cdot \underline{\check{N}D} \cdot \underline{\check{N}D} \cdot \underline{NP_2}$ C.M. S Spr S _{ni} S _{dan} Vf
(2) Gullarni uch kun oldin qizi bolalar bog'chasidan ... uzib kelgandi		
	J .M.	$\underline{\check{N}D} \cdot \underline{\check{N}D} \cdot \underline{NP_1} \cdot \underline{\check{N}D} \cdot \underline{NP_2}$ C.M. S _{ni} NmSAdv S _i S _{dan} Vf
(3) Bolalar nega hech narsa yeyishmaydi		
	J .M.	$\underline{NP_1} \cdot \underline{\check{N}D} \cdot \underline{\check{N}D} \cdot \underline{NP_2}$ C.M. S Pn _{int} Pn _{ng} ng Vf

(4) <i>U ... maysalarning jozibasini o'ziga singdirolmadi</i>		
	J .M.	$\frac{NP_1 \cdot \tilde{N}D \cdot \tilde{N}D \cdot NP_2}{Pn_p \quad S_{ps} \quad S_{ni} \quad ngVf}$ C.M.
(5) <i>Buning yorqin misolini Hasan ikki marta boshidan o'tkazdi</i>		
	J .M.	$\frac{\tilde{N}D \cdot \tilde{N}D \cdot \tilde{N}D \cdot NP_1 \cdot \tilde{N}D \cdot NP_2}{Pn_{dem} \quad A \quad S_{ni} \quad S \quad NmS \quad Vf}$

Non-nuclear dependent components can be represented by the transitive form of the verb, the NP2 component represented by the verb, and the noun can be defined by the name of the action.

6. *Ular ... baqirib-baqirib gapirishardi* (QA, 70).

7. *Har bir inson qalbida olam bilan uyg'unlashishga tashnalik bor* (ENYH, 21).

$\tilde{N}D$ in the sixth sentence *baqirib-baqirib* element NP_1 (*Ular*) NP_2 (*gapirishardi*) refers to the process of the expressed action. The seventh sentence contains five subordinate components, one of which is an action noun with a suffix (*uyg'unlashishga*) to NP_1 , one is a noun with a locative suffix (*qalbida*) to NP_2 , the other three are subject to other $\tilde{N}D$. In this case, it is a noun in the accusative form without a marker (*inson* → *insonning*) an antecedent collective pronoun subordinate to the subordinate clause of NP_2 (*Har bir*) in relation to $\tilde{N}D$ represented. The last subordinate clause in this sentence (*olam bilan*) expressed by a noun and subordinated to the name of the action with the help of an auxiliary.

6) <i>Ular ... baqirib-baqirib gapirishardi</i>		
	J .M.	$\frac{NP_1 \cdot \tilde{N}D \cdot NP_2}{Pn_p \quad V_{rav}V_{rav} \quad Vf}$ C.M.
7) <i>Har bir inson qalbida olam bilan uyg'unlashishga tashnalik bor</i>		
	J.M.	
$\tilde{N}D \cdot \tilde{N}D \cdot \tilde{N}D \cdot \tilde{N}D \cdot \tilde{N}D \cdot NP_1 \cdot NP_2$ $P_{ind} \quad S_{ps} \quad S_{da} \quad Spr \quad V_{inf} \quad S \quad mw$		C.M.

A non-nuclear dependent component can also be expressed by an abstract noun, a possessive adjective, a number, an adjective, and a phrase denoting the action process. Also, it was observed that the non-nuclear dependent component can be subordinate not only to the core predicative or non-nuclear dependent components, but also to the non-nuclear predicative 2 component.

8. *Bo'yoqchilik bilan ish bitmaydi* (QA, 84).

9. *Bu kecha ko'kda tantana bo'layotgandi* (QA, 98).

10. *Hasan bo'lim xonasida ofitserni rangsiz bir yuz ila kutayotganini ko'rdi* (QA, 135).

11. *Uning o'ttiz ming qo'shini tarqab ketibdi* (PQ, 165).

12. *Bu safar chol uzoq, to'xtovsiz yo'taldi* (O'H, 6).

13. *... yosh o'rikning qizg'ish novdalari hamon qattiq-qattiq silkinar edi* (O'H, 9).

14. *Hammasi bir kiprik qoqqulik fursatda o'tib ketdi* (O'H, 25).

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In the eighth sentence under analysis, the action noun is activated with the help of an auxiliary (*Bo'yoqchilik bilan ish bitmaydi*) *nima bilan emas qanday* is an answer to the question and is subject to NP2. In the following sentences, subordinate components signifying space, add the suffix of place-time agreement (-da) received adjective (*ko'kda*), noun (*bo'lim xonasida*) intransitive (*bo'layotgandi*) and transitive (*ko'rdi*) attached to verbs. Also, *rangsiz bir yuz ila* (10) – subordinate clause is subject to ÑP2 and means the status of ÑP1. Number (*o'ttiz ming*) with ÑD noun (*qo'shini*) blan indicates the amount of NP1 expressed. Instead of ÑD *Bu safar* (12) syntactic unit demonstrative pronoun + noun and served to mean the repetition of the action. Next subordinate components in the sentence (*uzoq, to'xtovsiz*) not monovalent, they are considered bivalent because they are cohesive fragments.

In the next sentence (13), ÑD is replaced by three kinds of adjectives: the original adjective of the simple level (*yosh*) to the noun in the accusative case (*o'rikning*) subjunctive, diminutive (*qizg'ish*) NP1 to the noun in place (*novdalari*), repeated adjective (*qattiq-qattiq*) intransitive verb (*silkinar edi*) is subject to the NP2 component represented by and participates in the sentence in the form of subordinate communication. In the next sentence, ÑD is a phraseological unit (*bir kiprik qoqqulik fursatda*) expressed by and subject to NP2. The component and conjunction models of sentences are as follows:

8) <i>Bo'yoqchilik bilan ish bitmaydi</i>	
	J .M. ÑD . NP1 . NP2 C.M. Spr S ngVf
9) <i>Bu kecha ko'kda tantana bo'layotgandi</i>	
	J .M. ÑD . ÑD . NP1 . NP2 C.M. PndemS Sda S Vf
10) <i>Hasan bo'lim xonasida ofitserni rangsiz bir yuz ila kutayotganini ko'rdi</i>	
	J.M.
$\frac{NP_1 \cdot \dot{N}D \cdot \dot{N}P_1 \cdot \dot{N}D \cdot \dot{N}D \cdot \dot{N}D \cdot \dot{N}P_2 \cdot NP_2}{S \quad SSda \quad Sni \quad A \quad Pnind \quad Spr \quad Vp1 \quad Vf} \quad C.M.$	
11) <i>Uning o'ttiz ming qo'shini tarqab ketibdi</i>	
	J. M. ÑD . ÑD . NP1 . NP2 C.M. Pnps Nm S Vf
12) <i>Bu safar chol uzoq, to'xtovsiz yo'taldi</i>	
	.M. ÑD . NP1 . IHÑD . IIHÑD . NP2 C.M. PndemS S A A Vf
13) ... <i>yosh o'rikning qizg'ish novdalari hamon qattiq-qattiq silkinar edi</i>	

	J.M.
$\checkmark\checkmark\checkmark\checkmark\checkmark\checkmark\checkmark\checkmark$ $A \quad S_{ps} \quad A \quad S \quad Adv \quad A \quad Vf$	C.M.
<i>14) Hammasi bir kiprik qoqqulik fursatda o'tib ketdi</i>	
	$\checkmark\checkmark\checkmark\checkmark\checkmark\checkmark\checkmark\checkmark$ $NP_1 \cdot \checkmark\checkmark \cdot \checkmark\checkmark \cdot NP_2$ $Pn_{ind} \quad Phr \quad S \quad Vf$

Xulosa

In English, non-nuclear subordinate components can appear in all places of the sentence, they can depend on both the core component and the subordinate component, and they are in preposition or postposition in relation to the main component. Also, a univalent subordinate clause can be represented by a noun, adjective, number, infinitive conjunction and pronoun.

The expression of non-nuclear dependent components in the Uzbek language is partially different from the English language. In the Uzbek language, the subordinate components are mainly placed before the dominant components, that is, they come in the preposition position, the postposition position is almost never observed. From the analysis of examples collected in the Uzbek language, it was found that non-core subordinate components are placed before the main component, one sentence can contain up to eight to ten subordinate clauses, which are both core clauses and subordinate clauses. can be connected on the basis of a subordinate relationship, one syntactic clause can be both a subordinate and a governing clause at the same time. Non-nuclear dependent components can be represented by nouns, adjectives, numbers, pronouns, functional forms of verbs. Nouns in the indicative and accusative cases are often used without an indicator in place of $\checkmark\checkmark$, in which case they do not have an additional determiner.

Unlike the English language, in Uzbek, $\checkmark\checkmark$ components do not occur with nouns in the form of the head agreement (except for noun + noun determiner + definite pattern), this situation is explained by the fact that the Uzbek language belongs to the system of inflectional languages.

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